

Green Fabrication of Cu-Doped Silver Nanoparticles Using *Abutilon indicum* and Their Dual Antibacterial and Anticancer Efficacy

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ABSTRACT

In this study employed eco-friendly and economical nanotechnology approach. The objective of the current study was to examine the green synthesis of Cu doped silver nanoparticles (Cu-AgNPs) using AI (*ABUTILON INDICUM*) leaf extract to cancer effects by biologically synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles in cancer cell lines, and to compare their anti-cancer potential with commercial Cu doped silver nanoparticles. Ultraviolet-Visible spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) analysis, Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDAX), Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy(FESEM) and Zeta potential, the characteristics and morphology of the photo-synthesized Cu doped AgNPs were assessed.

Key words: Cu doped Silver nanoparticles, Green synthesis, Leaf extract, Antibacterial activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The focus of the current generation is on nanoparticles and nanotechnology. The field has incorporated applications ranging from used in daily life to those used in armories and space exploration as well as human cosmetics and medicine [1]. Thin films, nanowires, and nanoparticles can all be used in technological applications of nanoscience [2]. The usage of nanoparticles in food preservatives, medications, and cosmetics that come into direct touch with people has increased significantly in recent years [3]. In particular, antibacterial activity, drug

delivery, and cancer therapy are utilized with metal oxides and metal nanoparticles such as silver, gold, ruthenium, palladium, platinum, iron oxide, rare-earth oxides, and silver nanoparticles. [4-7].

Recent research by Alharbiet al. provided data on the environmentally friendly manufacture of silver nanoparticles utilizing a different plant extracts. As a result, the various bacterial strains exhibit prominent cell damage from the resulting silver nanoparticles. Unlike Gram-Positive bacteria, whose cell walls are more resistant to synthesized nanoparticles, this silver nanoparticle is more effective against Gram- Negative bacteria. The chemical makeup of the plant extract, its concentration, the concentration of AgNO_3 , the extraction solvent, the extraction time and temperature, the extraction value, the reaction time and temperature, and others were discussed and reported in this study [8].

Vathana et al explained about one out of every three people will develop cancer at a certain point in their lives, which is a significant life-threatening condition. The development of nanomaterials that precisely target the intended cells or tissues while having no adverse effects is both important and fascinating for researchers. Anticancer effects are observed in both in vitro and in vivo model systems.

Additionally, the effects of fluorouracil on cells that express the uracil phosphoribosyl enzyme (UPRT) and cells that do not produce the enzyme on cell death, as well as how AgNPs cause cancer cells to become more sensitive and induce apoptosis, were investigated. After being coated with starch, they revealed anticancer effects in both glioblastoma and healthy human lung fibroblast cells. AgNPs mediated by plant extracts have been shown to selectively cytotoxicity kill cancer cells in human lungs [9].

These days, toothpaste, cosmetics, soap and shampoo all include metal nanoparticles. Due to the range of uses it has in chemistry, water management, optical sensors, adsorption, and medicinal administration. The environmentally friendly synthesis of silver nanoparticles has proven to be one of the most exciting fields of possible medical research. Because nanomedicine and other subfields of nanotechnology do not rely on hazardous chemicals, high pressure, high energy, or high temperatures, they have a significant impact on therapeutic healthcare [10].

The present work reports the biosynthesis processes allowed for the green synthesis of silver nanoparticles. By using X-ray diffraction techniques, the structural and crystallographic characterization of the produced nanoparticles was carried out. By using field emission scanning electron microscopy, the particles were morphologically identified. In addition, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and ultraviolet analysis were used to examine the spectroscopic

features of silver nanoparticles. Using a particle analyzer, the zeta potential of the biosynthesized nanoparticles was tested. This work revealed good antibacterial and anticancer activity to demonstrate their respective capabilities.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Collection of Plant Material and Preparation of Leaf Extract

Abutilon Indicum is a broadleaf weed that grows on land. Abutilon Indicum whole green leaves was collected from Erode district (Tamil Nadu-India) and to rid the dirt pieces as in Fig 1. After being washed thoroughly with water, the leaves were dried in the shade. Then, using scissor 30 g of leaves were cut into tiny pieces. Chopped leaves were stirred on 100 ml of double-distilled water in an Erlenmeyer flask at 70°C for 30 minutes. After allowing the extract cool, Whatman filter paper was used to filter it.

2.2 Green Synthesis of Silver Nanoparticles

Take an 80ml serving of distilled water in a beaker, add 0.2 M of AgNO₃ & 0.1 M of Copper Nitrate and stir it for 20 minutes at 70 °C. 20 ml of Abutilon Indicum leaf extract was added to the AgNO₃ (80ml) solution. The mixture was then heated at 70°C for 20 minutes with constant stirring. The formation of AgNPs was preliminarily detected by change in mixture solution colour from Pale green to brown. Obtained materials were centrifuged and final material was dried at 70°C for 2 hr. Fine powder was collected for evaluation [11].

Fig 1 Abutilon Indicum Plant

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 XRD ANALYSIS OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Using X-ray diffraction techniques, the structural and crystallographic characterization of the produced nanoparticles was carried out. Cu doped Silver nanoparticles exhibit strong diffraction peaks, which are readily apparent. As in Fig.2 the obtained data was matched with standard JCPDS file no. 04-0783, the peaks are identical [12].

The 2θ values for the highest six peaks are 19.5743, 21.6427, 24.8371, 29.6094, 32.7319 and 35.4277 which corresponds to lattice planes at (111), (102), (112), (211), (122) and (101)

respectively. Indicating that they have an Cu doped AgNPs structure with a face-centered cubic structure. The average crystallite sizes of the generated nanoparticles were calculated using the Debye-Scherrer equation to be between 30-40 nm. [13]

Figure 2 X-ray diffraction pattern of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

3.2 FESEM ANALYSIS OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Cu doped AgNPs were measured using FESEM to determine their size and surface Morphology. The FESEM picture of the green-synthesised AI-Cu doped AgNPs is seen in Figure 3a and 3b. The figure 3a shows the 200 nm intensification shape and Figure 3b shows the 100 nm enlargement. The green synthesized AI-Cu doped AgNPs' spherical with Cluster shape was visible in the FESEM pictures. The FESEM pictures further demonstrated the homogeneous distribution of the synthesized AI-Cu doped AgNPs. The produced nanoparticles had an observed average size of 30–40 nm [14].

Figure 3(a) and Figure 3(b) Scanning electron microscopy of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

3.3 EDAX ANALYSIS OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

The results of EDAX were confirmed to be able to green-synthesize Cu doped silver nanoparticles with biological components from *Abutilon Indicum* leaf extract. The EDAX spectrum shows three peaks at 2.97 keV, 3.79 keV, and 0.35 keV mentioned in Fig. 4. The first-

highest peak reveals a significant quantity of silver content. The existence of at least a small quantity of oxygen content is shown by the second highest peak. The copper concentration at this time is seen by the third-highest peak. The leaf extract has already demonstrated this copper content [15].

Figure 4 Energy Dispersive X ray diffraction of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

Name of the element	Presence in atoms (wt.%)	Level
Silver	78.94	Maximum
Oxygen	18.57	Minimum
Copper	02.49	Small amount

Table 1. EDAX of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

3.4 FTIR ANALYSIS OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Figure 5, illustrates the surface composition of Cu doped silver nanoparticles made with Abutilon Indicum plant extracts that was determined by FTIR spectroscopy [16]. This novel method is utilized to identify functional groups that are encircling or capping the Cu doped silver nanoparticles' surface.

Figure.5 further demonstrates that Abutilon Indicum plant extracts are used to minimize the generated Cu doped silver nanoparticles. When Cu doped silver nanoparticles are reduced using extracts from Abutilon Indicum plants, the observed peaks become more obvious [17]. The bands at 3615 cm^{-1} is observed from the present O-H stretching bond. The band near at 2896 cm^{-1} is observed from the present of C-H stretching bond. The intense peak at 1959 cm^{-1} depicts the C-H bonding.

Figure 5 FTIR spectra of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

3.5 UV-VIS SPECTROSCOPY OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Fig. 6 reveals the generation of synthesized Cu doped AgNPs in a solution, can be confirmed by the absorbance spectra. The study calculates the amount of light that passes through the sample and contrasts with an estimate of light's incident source. The common wavelength range for nanoparticle detection is 200–800 nm. Surface plasmon resonance is known to be induced by Cu doped AgNPs at a particular range of wavelengths. Lower and higher maximum wavelength values are connected with smaller average size and higher concentration of Cu doped silver nanoparticles, respectively. In our result, the synthesized Cu doped AgNPs absorption peaks in the visible region at 273 nm and absorbance was 0.309.

Moreover, SPR images of same wavelengths obtained using UV visible spectroscopy reveals that the green produced Cu doped silver nanoparticles can keep their stability for several months [18]. A useful method for characterizing manufactured Cu doped silver nanoparticles is UV visible spectroscopy, which was used to analyze the spectroscopic results of AgNPs produced by leaf extracts from the *Abutilon Indicum* plant. Table 2 shows the absorption peak with respective wavelengths.

Figure 6 UV-Visible spectroscopy of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

No.	Wavelength (nm)	Absorption
1	363	0.181
2	273	0.309
3	203	1.971

Table 2. UV-VIS absorption of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

3.6 PHOTOLUMINESCENCE ANALYSIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

The photoluminescence analysis of Cudoped AgNPs is illustrated in Fig. 6. This analysis demonstrates the emission of light from AgNPs after it has been absorbed by light particles (photons). AgNPs will emit light of a specific wavelength when they are activated by light of that wavelength. Even if it is evident in an excellent conductor like silver, it also depends on the particle's size, shape, and surroundings. Because of its various plasmonic modes, an anisotropic structure, such as nanoplates or nanorods, exhibits several emission bands. Applications such as biosensing, imaging, optoelectronic photocatalysis, and solar cell applications for good conductivity are explained by this analysis

Figure 6 PL spectroscopy of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

In this PL spectrum, $X = 361.07$ and $Y = 34.70$ is the main absorbed peaks. AgNPs' PL peak values, which exhibit plasmonic excitation and an inter band electronic transition, are located at 360 nm. The effective production of optically active AgNPs with a homogeneous particle size distribution is confirmed by the strong peak value. Because of its electronic transitions and surface plasmonic resonance effects, the treatment demonstrates the optical activity of AgNPs. High radiation recombination is reflected in the intensity increase up to the peak, and the curve declines beyond 365 nm. The potential use of AgNPs in solar cells, biosensors, optoelectronic devices, and bioimaging is known by this curve.

3.7 ZETA -POTENTIAL ANALYSIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

The dispersion of nanoparticles, stability, and effective surface electric charge are all significantly influenced by zeta potential. Based on the particle charge, the zeta potential is calculated by computing the peak area and peak number [19]. Stable particles have a low tendency to coalesce because of their enormous positive or negative charges, which cause them to resist one another. The zeta potential of stable suspensions is typically between 20 and 30 mV as in Fig. 7.

Figure 7 Zeta potential of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

The data potential of Cu doped AgNPs synthesized from leaf extract of *Abutilon Indicum* was 37 mV in contrast to extract exhibited potential value of 26.7 mV, indicating that particles were more stable. The surface charge of nanoparticles can also be affected by the solution; it is possible for an isometric point or surface charge to be 0 at a certain level. Determined the Zeta potential values of Cu doped AgNPs synthesized using *Abutilon Indicum*.

3.8 DLS PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

DLS used to investigate the surface charge size and particle size distribution of Cu doped Silver nanoparticles as shown in Fig 8. This method is based on interactions between Brownian spherical particles and light traveling through a colloidal solution. The hydrodynamic diameter can be calculated using the scattered intensities from time-dependent data [20]. The electrical layers on nanoparticle surfaces, as well as the capping agents and stabilizers present in solution, often have an effect on the hydrodynamic diameter of the particles. DLS can measure particles with diameters ranging from 40 to 500 nanometers, however it has difficulties measuring the size of agglomerated particles.

Figure 8 DLS particle size analyze of synthesized Cu doped silver nanoparticles

To avoid numerous scattering effects in DLS, only a modest number of nanoparticles are needed. DLS is more suited for monitoring aggregation during the initial process because it is susceptible to the availability of aggregates. The Abutilon Indicum-sourced synthetic Cu doped AgNPs appear to be a polydisperse combination of particles that hydrodynamic diameters ranging from 200 to 500 nm. Another study indicated that the average size rose as extract concentration was increased.

3.9 ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

The antimicrobials in the sample were allowed to interact with the test organisms on a freshly seeded plate as they diffused into the medium. A confluent lawn of growth will result, producing consistently round zones of inhibition. It is possible to measure the diameter of the zone of inhibition in millimeters [21]. As shown in Fig.9-12, Petri plates containing 20 ml nutrient agar medium were seeded with 24h culture of bacterial strains were adjusted to 0.5 OD value according to McFarland standard, (*Staphylococcus aureus* 902, *E.coli*-443, *Streptococcus pyogenes*-1928 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*-424) Wells were cut and concentration of sample AI, AM, LC, SG and CH (500, 250, 100 and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) was added. The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The antibacterial activity was assayed by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone formed around the wells. Gentamicin antibiotic was used as a positive control. The values were calculated using Graph Pad Prism 6.0 software (USA).

Figure 9 Staphylococcus aureus

Figure 10 E. Coli

Figure11 StreptococcusPyogenes

Figure 12 Pseudomonas aeruginosa

3.10 SOLAR CELL APPLICATION OF Cu DOPED SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Research on renewable energy is being revolutionized by nanotechnology, especially in the creation of sophisticated solar cell materials. Silver nanoparticles, or Ag NPs, are particularly interesting among the several nanostructures studied because of their significant optical absorption, specific surface plasmon resonance (SPR) characteristics, and capacity to improve charge transport in solar devices. However, pristine silver nanoparticles frequently encounter difficulties such as high cost, instability, and restricted band structure tunability. In an effort to get around these restrictions, scientists have concentrated on doping silver with transition metals like copper (Cu), which can drastically alter the nanoparticles' electrical, chemical, and physical characteristics and make them ideal for solar cell applications.

The electronic band structure is altered and new defect states are introduced when Ag NPs are doped with Cu. By expanding the nanoparticles' absorption spectrum into the visible spectrum, this modification can increase the effectiveness of light collecting. Since the production of electron-hole pairs in solar cells depends on efficient light absorption, Cu doping raises the likelihood of photon capture, which enhances the production of photocurrent. Additionally, by serving as trapping sites, Cu atoms can lower the rate at which charge carriers recombine, facilitating more effective electron and hole transport to the electrodes. This has a direct impact on raising the solar device's total power conversion efficiency (PCE).

Cu-doped Ag NPs have been shown to enhance fill factor, lower interfacial energy barriers, and boost carrier mobility when embedded in the active layer of perovskite solar cells. Likewise, in organic photovoltaics, these doped nanoparticles function as nano-antennas, more efficiently absorbing and disseminating light across the thin active regions. Cu-doped Ag NPs' many uses, including light trapping, improving stability, and enhancing charge separation, show how adaptable they are in increasing solar cell efficiency[29].

Cu-doped silver nanoparticles, in conclusion, present a viable solution to close the gap between effective solar energy harvesting and nanomaterials. These hybrid nanoparticles, which combine the electrical tunability and affordability of copper with the potent plasmonic qualities of silver, make promising candidates for next-generation solar cells. Future studies should concentrate on controlled synthesis and ideal doping concentrations.

4.CONCLUSION

The study lies in its simplicity and instantaneous synthesis of capped Cu -AgNPs with uniform size without use of any capping agent or template. Anticancer activity of cell line MCF7 was reacted. The reactivity of the extract with the cell line was low initial concentrations and found to increase with the increased concentrations which express the concentration dependent cytotoxicity potential of the extract. The antibacterial activity of the produced nanoparticles against *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* microorganisms was confirmed. Due to their antibacterial qualities, green produced silver nanoparticles could be highly helpful in the medical field.

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